

Phase-field modelling of failure in ceramics with multiscale porosity

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Abstract

Many stiff biological materials exhibiting outstanding compressive strength/weight ratio are characterized by high porosity, spanning different size-scales, typical examples being bone and wood. A successful bio-mimicking of these materials is provided by a recently obtained apatite, directly produced through a biomorphic transformation of natural wood and thus inheriting its highly hierarchical structure. This unique apatite (but also wood and bone) is characterized by two major distinct populations of differently-sized cylindrical voids, a porosity shown in the present paper to influence failure, both in terms of damage growth and fracture nucleation and propagation. This statement follows from failure analysis, developed through in-silico generation of artificial samples (reproducing the two-scale porosity of the material) and subsequent finite element modelling of damage, implemented with phase-field treatment for fracture growth. It is found that small voids promote damage nucleation and enhance bridging of macro-pores by micro-crack formation, while macro-pores influence the overall material response and drive the propagation of large fractures. Our results explain the important role of multiscale porosity characterizing stiff biological materials and lead to a new design paradigm, by introducing an in-silico tool to implement bio-mimicking in new artificial materials with brittle behaviour, such as carbide or ceramic foams.

Keywords: porous materials; multiscale porosity; bio-mimetic materials; phase field approach to fracture; finite element method.

1. Introduction

Materials characterized by a high-density distribution of voids are diffused in nature (for instance bone, wood, rock –sandstone, tuff, pumice–, coal) and as man-made materials (for instance concrete, cellular ceramic, and carbide foam). Wood and bone evidence populations of cylindrical pores with nearly circular cross-sections, ranging in diameter through multiple size scales, a feature affecting many of their physical [1–3] and mechanical [4–6] properties. Implementing size-scale variation in the porosity of artificial materials is a bio-mimicking challenge, particularly for bone substitutes and scaffolds [7–11]. A successful answer to this challenge was provided [12] through the synthesis of a new material, a 3-D porous apatite (called ‘Biomorphic Apatite’, BA in the following) obtained via a bio-morphic transformation of natural wood into ceramics, Fig. 1.

BA replicates the multiscale hierarchical structure of wood, with a double-sized porosity (Fig. 1), sharing similarities with bone and thus becoming ideal for bio-mechanical applications, where outstanding strength and fracture energy absorption are crucially important [1, 13]. Here, a correct failure analysis may lead to the design of surgical interventions and prediction of rehabilitation times so that the development of a numerical tool for this analysis is the object of the present paper. A class of materials (including those

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Fig. 1 | Crack propagation in Biomorphic Apatite, characterized by a multiscale porosity. Left: SEM image of a BA sample characterized by the presence of macro (green arrows) and meso (red arrows) cylindrical pores with a nearly circular cross-section. The sample was subjected to uniaxial compression test. Right: a magnified detail of the sample on the left shows a crack (highlighted white) which nucleated, almost parallel to the direction of loading, from the external surface of a macro pore, where tensile stress locally develops, although the mean stress in the sample is compressive.

addressed here, plus glass, ceramic, rock and concrete) are brittle so that fracture nucleates primarily under tensile stresses. Under overall compression, crack generation is complicated by the presence of voids, which concentrate tensile stress near their boundary and stimulate fracture growth parallel to the loading direction [14–16], see Fig. 1. Fracture patterns are typically tortuous and difficult to follow or model analytically [17], so that numerical techniques play a decisive role. These can be classified as: (i.) augmented versions of the finite-element method [18] (such as cohesive-zone methods, CZM, or extended finite-element methods, XFEM, the former requiring an initial knowledge of the crack pattern and the latter an *ad hoc* constitutive relation at the crack tip); (ii.) diffusive damage models [19–22] (relying on a regularized crack topology); (iii.) the phase-field approach, overcoming the difficulties encountered in the other techniques by allowing damage to grow within a thin portion of the material. The latter technique has been developed as an energy minimization, via Γ -convergence regularization of free discontinuities to model cracks [23–30] and was recently proven to be particularly suitable for the description of complex fracture patterns in PMMA samples with notches and holes [31] and therefore is adopted here.

The porosity typical of biomorphic apatite is primarily double-sized so that macro-scale pores can be differentiated from meso-scale pores, Fig. 1 (micropores, also present, are neglected as they were found not to influence fracture) and is shown to correspond to two peaks of a probability density function. This function allows the set-up of a numerical tool for the generation of in-silico porous samples, to be used for subsequent fracture simulation using the phase-field technique.

The simulations show that the porosity is always connected to a reduction of the overall stiffness and strength of the material. However, the meso-scale porosity produces: (i.) a smearing of damage through zones that would remain intact in the absence of this scale of pores; (ii.) a shielding of regions of the material from cracks; and (iii.) a promotion of fracture growth in other zones.

Our results show that, not only the value of ‘total porosity’ is relevant to the mechanical modeling of porous-brittle solids, but also the amount of fractions of porosity with different characteristic size plays a decisive role, a result with implications in the simulation of fracture in biological porous materials, such as bone or wood, and in porous ceramics for bone repair or for filters used in industrial applications.

2. Results

2.1. Theory

In a purely isothermal formulation of a brittle-damaging material, where the damage only occurs for tensile strains, the Helmholtz free energy per unit volume can be represented as

$$\psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, s) = [(1 - s)^2 + k] \psi_+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \psi_-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}), \quad (1)$$

a function of a damage parameter $s \in [1 - \sqrt{1 - k}, 1]$, where $k > 0$ represents a residual stiffness and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain. Note that the lower bound of the range of variation for s corresponds to an intact material, while $s = 1$ to a fully damaged one. Equation (1) embodies an additive split of the elastic energy $\psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ into tensile, ‘+’, and compressive, ‘-’, strains

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\pm} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \langle \varepsilon_i \rangle_{\pm} \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_i, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{e}_i and ε_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are the unit eigenvectors and corresponding eigenvalues of the strain, respectively, and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the Macaulay bracket operator, defined for every scalar x as $\langle x \rangle_{\pm} = (x \pm |x|)/2$. Following [29] the tensile and compressive parts of the strain energy density assume the following expression:

$$\psi_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\lambda}{2} \langle \pm \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rangle^2 + \mu \text{tr} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\pm}^2), \quad (3)$$

where λ and μ are the Lamé constants and $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ denotes the trace operator.

The Helmholtz free energy, Eq.(1), defines a diffuse and isotropic damage model, where damage only occurs in tension, so that the stress tensor

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, s) = \frac{\partial \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, s)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}, \quad (4)$$

becomes the work-conjugate to the strain and is represented as the sum between tensile and compressive components, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_-$, both related to the strains through the isotropic elasticity tensor \mathbb{C} as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_+ = [(1 - s)^2 + k] \mathbb{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_+, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_- = \mathbb{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_-. \quad (5)$$

Following the variational approach to brittle fracture, propagation and branching of a crack in a damaging solid can be found as the result of the minimization of the energy functional [29, 32]

$$\Pi(\mathbf{u}, s, \Gamma) = \int_{\Omega \setminus \Gamma} \psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, s) \, d\mathbf{x} + \int_{\Gamma} \mathcal{G}_c(s) \, d\Gamma, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the displacement, \mathcal{G}_c is the fracture energy and Γ is the (unknown and evolving) fracture path inside the body Ω .

A direct use of the functional (6) involves the solution of a free boundary value problem, which can be approximated by following the regularized framework introduced with the phase field approach [24, 29]. The approximation regards the topology of the crack, which is smeared out onto the whole body, allowing to rewrite the potential energy of the system as a volume integral

$$\Pi(\mathbf{u}, s) = \int_{\Omega} [\psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, s) + G_c \gamma(s, \nabla s)] \, d\mathbf{x}, \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma(s, \nabla s)$ is the crack density functional, depending on the spatial gradient $\nabla \cdot$ of the internal state variable s , now called ‘phase field variable’.

The surface Γ , not explicitly present in the functional (7), can be recovered as the result of an energy minimization procedure. In particular, introducing the so-called ‘AT2 model’ [26, 29], the functional $\gamma(s, \nabla s)$, is represented by the following convex function

$$\gamma(s, \nabla s) = \frac{1}{2l} s^2 + \frac{l}{2} |\nabla s|^2, \quad (8)$$

where l is a regularization characteristic length, related to the smeared crack width. For a sufficiently small l , the minimization of functional (7), implemented with the nonlocal crack density function (8), ‘spontaneously’ leads to a solution where the damage is strongly localized near a surface Γ , representing a crack. Formally, it can be demonstrated that, for vanishing regularization parameter ($l \rightarrow 0$), the formulation outlined in Eq.(7) tends to Eq.(6) in the sense of the so-called ‘ Γ -convergence’ [28].

Finally, the weak form of the variational problem, and the consequent finite-element discretization, can be found in [31].

3. Virtual testing

3.1. Two scale porosity and mesh generation

A brittle porous material is now considered, characterized by a two-scale cylindrical porosity. A two-dimensional formulation fits the specific *transverse* structure that biomorphic apatite (‘BA’ henceforth) inherits from rattan wood, which presents elongated grains and parallel channels, with approximately circular cross-section and two predominant sizes (Fig. 1).

The BA samples are characterized by three size-levels of porosity $0 \leq \Phi \leq 1$ (defined as the ratio between the volume of voids and the total volume of the element in a representative volume element), namely, macroscopic (approximately $300 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter), mesoscopic (up to $50 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter), and microscopic ($1 \mu\text{m}$ of diameter) [1]. Thus, while the size ratio between mesoporosity and macroporosity ranges within the interval $(1/15, 1/2)$, the size ratio between microporosity and macroporosity is smaller than $1/100$. Therefore, the microporosity has then been assumed to be part of the matrix. Using an *ad hoc* developed Matlab code (based on image analysis functions ‘imread’ and ‘imfindcircles’, available in the complementary material), the porosity of BA, as characterized from SEM photomicrographs, was shown to obey to the following probability distribution function (PDF)

$$f = 16.82 e^{-889.1(r-0.16)^2} + 72.24 e^{-16396(r-0.02)^2}, \quad (9)$$

which exhibits a bi-modal shape, clearly visible in Fig. 2 (black dashed curve).

The peak on the right of the curve occurs at high values of void radius and is representative of macroporosity Φ_{macro} , while the peak on the left is representative of meso-porosity Φ_{meso} , so that, neglecting the micro level, the total porosity is the sum of the two following major contributions $\Phi = \Phi_{\text{macro}} + \Phi_{\text{meso}}$.

The obtained PDF was used for in-silico generation (through random placement of non-overlapping voids) of samples of porous materials (an example is shown in the inset of Fig. 2), needed for simulations (performed at the Laboratory for Numerical Modelling of Materials of the University of Trento, using a Workstation AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO 5995WX, 512GB RAM, 2 GeForce RTX 3090 graphic cards, acquired with the ERC-AdG-2021-101052956-Beyond), via the previously outlined phase-field approach.

In order to investigate the influence of two size-scale porosity on crack patterns in ceramic materials subject to uniaxial compression, a preliminary calibration (reported in the supporting material) on single-porosity samples [generated by simply neglecting the right term in equation (9)] has been performed for both mechanical model and mesh size for subsequent finite element solution. The results of this analysis are shown in the supporting material.

For a material characterized by a porosity Φ , independently of the number of size-scales of porosity, the overall stiffness of an equivalent homogeneous material can theoretically be estimated in a number of ways. For spherical voids, results applicable to ceramic materials were provided in [33–35]. For cylindrical voids,

Fig. 2 | Size distribution of voids in Biomorphic Apatite, characterized by multiscale porosity. Probability density function (PDF, shown dashed) obtained from SEM photomicrographs of BA samples, modelling their void distribution in terms of the voids' radius, r . The BA specimens evidence a bimodal distribution of void radii typical of a double porosity (macro-porosity is marked in blue, while meso-porosity in green). The inset shows a sample generated in-silico with the PDF reported in Fig. (black dashed curve), which has been coupled with a random generator to impose the position of the voids' center.

the generalized self-consistent homogenization scheme [36] is followed. The effective Young's modulus \bar{E} , defining a homogeneous elastic solid under plane stress, is given by

$$\frac{\bar{E}}{E_{\text{matrix}}} = \frac{\Phi(1 - 2\Phi - \Phi^2) + \sqrt{(1 + \Phi + \Phi^2 + \Phi^3)^2 - 12\Phi^2}}{1 + 5\Phi + 2\Phi^2}, \quad (10)$$

which will be used in the following as a reference.

The peak stress under increasing uniaxial stress $\bar{\sigma}$ (corresponding to failure in a force-controlled testing device), for a sample made of an equivalent homogeneous material, is assumed to follow the simple rule [37]

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_{\text{matrix}}} = e^{-b\Phi}, \quad (11)$$

where σ_{matrix} is the peak (or failure) stress in the matrix material and b a coefficient to be fitted with measurements, which in our case was found to be $b \approx 6.17$.

Equations (10) and (11) are used as a reference in the simulations, in particular, once Young's modulus and failure stress of the matrix material are assigned for numerical calculations, the above equations are employed to obtain an expected 'rough' behavior of porous samples. Simulations of uniaxial compression tests have been performed for values of (single-scale) macro-porosity equal to {5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35%, 40%} (see Fig. 3, upper part), and the material parameters used throughout the numerical simulations are: $E = 70$ MPa, $\nu = 0,25$, $G_c = 0.0025$ MPa mm, $l = 0.12$ mm. For each value of porosity, ten specimens with different distributions of pores have been considered and, accordingly, ten different overall stress/strain responses have been obtained [in terms of $\bar{\sigma} = (\text{measured force})/(\text{cross-section area})$ and $\bar{\epsilon} = (\text{applied displacement})/L$]. For each value of macro-porosity (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35%, 40%) the mean response evaluated over ten simulated stress-strain curves is reported in Fig. 3. Further results for three (of the ten) samples characterized by a macro porosity of 20% are shown in Fig. 4.

Here, in full agreement with experimental results, simulations show that the response of the specimens remains almost linear until a peak value of stress is reached, and it is followed by a softening branch, due to the coalescence of small cracks.

It should be noted that the overall stress/strain curves shown in Fig. 4 are plotted up to values of overall strain equal to 0.11. Although moderately high, these strains can be decomposed into small strains in the

Fig. 3 | Response to compression of biomorphic apatite, where only one scale of porosity is considered. Mean value (over 10 different porosity distributions) of the stress-strain response for single-porosity samples, for different values of macro-porosity, Φ_{macro} . A qualitative example of the analyzed in-silico generated sample with the prescribed boundary conditions is shown in the left inset of the stress-strain plot.

matrix material and rigid-body displacements related to failure. Therefore, local strains remain moderate, as further detailed in the Supporting material.

The shape of the softening branch and the value of the peak stress greatly depend on the geometrical distribution of voids, while the stiffness (the tangent line to the stress-strain curve) is only slightly influenced. Fig. 4 is enhanced with insets, showing crack growth at different test stages, developing parallel to the direction of applied loading. The last feature, agreeing with experiments, reveals that the model can effectively capture damage nucleation, fracture propagation and the final failure mechanism.

The mean value and standard deviation of overall stiffness (Young's modulus \bar{E}) and strength (peak stress $\bar{\sigma}$) are reported in Table 1, evaluated using simulations pertaining to the ten specimens tested for each porosity level. Predictions obtained with Eqs.(10) and (11) are included in parentheses and show a tight agreement with the numerical values. It can be noted from the table that at an increase of macro-porosity,

	$\Phi_{\text{macro}} = 5\%$	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%	35%	40%
Mean(\bar{E})	61.9 (60.4)	55.2 (52.3)	49.1 (45.1)	43.5 (38.7)	38.9 (32.9)	34.4 (27.6)	29.8 (22.7)	25.2 (18.2)
Mean($\bar{\sigma}$)	4.53 (5.38)	3.34 (3.99)	2.76 (2.96)	2.13 (2.19)	1.76 (1.62)	1.53 (1.20)	1.25 (0.89)	1.04 (0.66)
St. Dev(\bar{E})	0.17	0.22	0.79	1.06	1.15	1.29	0.46	1.57
St. Dev($\bar{\sigma}$)	0.17	0.17	0.23	0.18	0.21	0.18	0.08	0.12

Table 1 | Overall properties of compressed Biomorphic Apatite samples (generated in silico), where only one scale of porosity is considered. Mean value (denoted as 'Mean') and standard deviation (denoted as 'St. Dev') of overall Young's Modulus \bar{E} and peak stress $\bar{\sigma}$ for different values of macro-porosity, as obtained from simulations of compression tests. Quantities are expressed in MPa. Values obtained with the self-consistent method and that proposed by Rice, respectively Eqs. (10) and (11), are reported in parentheses.

the effect of the void distribution on the overall strength tends to decrease, while the stiffness remains almost constant.

Fig. 4| Compression behavior of a simulated biomorphic apatite, where only one scale of porosity is considered, using phase-field. Simulated overall stress-strain responses for three samples with the same porosity 20%, but different void distributions. The progressive crack formation and growth, developing parallel to the load direction, is reported at increasing values of overall strain $\bar{\epsilon}$ in the inset for the sample with $\Phi_{\text{macro}} = 20\%$ shown unloaded in Fig. 3 of the supporting material. Note the strong effect of crack propagation on the overall stress-strain curves.

Fig. 5 summarizes results for specimens characterized by a single-scale porosity, by displaying values of peak stress and stiffness, as functions of the amount of porosity. Data agree well with predictions from micromechanical models, Eqs. (10) and (11).

Fig. 5| Overall response of in-silico generated samples of Biomorphic Apatite, where only one scale of porosity is considered. Simulated overall peak stress $\bar{\sigma}$ (triangular spots) and overall Young's Modulus \bar{E} (square spots) as functions of macro-porosity, Φ_{macro} . Theoretical predictions from micromechanical models, Eqs. (10) and (11), respectively denoted with 'GSCM' and 'Rice', are also reported.

3.2. Compression test on porous brittle solids: two-scale porosity

The phase-field approach to fracture mechanics is shown now to answer several questions that may arise when modeling or designing functional porous ceramics. In particular, at a fixed value of total porosity (7 values are explored, see Appendix A.6), simulations on in-silico created samples are used with different percentages of macro and meso voids, to explore effects related to second-scale porosity on: (i.) overall Young's modulus, (ii.) failure stress, (iii.) crack growth, and (iv.) damage diffusion.

Overall stress/strain curves, analogous to those presented in Fig. 4, but now computed for double-scale porosity, are depicted in Fig. 6. Here, the total porosity (sum of the macro and meso values, $\Phi = \Phi_{\text{macro}} + \Phi_{\text{meso}}$) is assumed to be equal to 25% (left) and 40% (right). Each curve represents the response of a sample in which the overall porosity is achieved by mixing different portions of macro-pores and meso-pores, where the former pores have a larger size than the latter, according to the PDF, Eq. (9). The peaks of the curves shown in Fig. 6 reveal that a superior mechanical response for specimens follows from an increase in the percentage of meso-pores. The left image of the same figure shows a specimen with total porosity of 25% split in macro-porosity and meso-porosity as follows: the red dot-dashed curve is characterized by 25% of macro-porosity, the blue one by 20% macro-porosity and 5% meso-porosity, and lastly, the black dashed one by 15% macro-porosity and 10% meso-porosity. The image on the right shows the effect is reproduced also for a total porosity of 40%. Note that the figure also reports (in green) the mean value of peak stress, 2.12 MPa, obtained from 4 experiments on biomorphic apatite, as reported in Table 2, which agrees very well with the simulations. The table reports also the value of peak stress as obtained from the simulation with the void distribution tighter to the real specimens.

Fig. 6 | Influence of multiscale porosity on the overall behavior of Biomorphic Apatite samples (generated in silico). The effects related to the presence of meso-pores are visible in the simulated overall stress-strain responses for samples characterized by the same value of total porosity Φ (25% on the left and 40% on the right), but different amounts of meso Φ_{meso} and macro Φ_{macro} porosity. The Young's modulus $E = \tan \theta$ and peak stress $\bar{\sigma}_{\text{peak}}$, Eqs.(10) and (11), are included. Peak stress and elastic stiffness increase when the density of meso-pores is increased. The value $\sigma = 2.12$ MPa reported in green is the mean value of peak stress measured on 4 compression tests on biomorphic apatite, very well captured by the simulations.

	Numerical	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Mean
Peak Stress [MPa]	2.06	2.33	2.17	2.03	1.93	2.12

Table 2 | Comparison between the peak stress resulting from a numerical simulation (using the phase-field technique on a sample with a porosity distribution representative of the real specimens) and from a compression test on four samples of a Biomorphic Apatite with 27% porosity (Samples 1–4).

Overall properties, in terms of peak strength and elastic modulus, for different specimens are shown in Fig. 7, as functions of the total porosity, but for different values of meso (and thus also macro) porosity. According to [38], the figure reveals that for a fixed value of total porosity, samples display improved mechanical properties at low macro porosity (triangles are located clearly above the trend lines). Therefore, macro porosity is more detrimental to stiffness and strength than meso-porosity. However, our computations show that this is not a strict rule, as evidenced in the inset of Fig. 7, showing that a sample at 0.35 total-porosity with 0.03 meso-porosity is less stiff and resistant than the sample with null meso-porosity. This feature is not isolated and occurs also at $\Phi = 0.2$ and is related to the particular geometrical distribution of voids and prompts the idea that the design of the spatial void distribution (possible via phase field) could improve material performances.

Both scales of porosity are found to concur in producing a non-linear effect on the overall properties

Fig. 7 | Overall properties of Biomorphic Apatite samples (generated in silico), with pores of different sizes. Simulated dimensionless Young’s modulus (red symbols) and peak stress (blue symbols) versus total porosity for samples characterized by double porosity. The inset shows that at $\Phi = 0.35$, the presence of a 0.03 fraction of meso-porosity can (surprisingly and contrary to most of the results) lead to a smaller stiffness and strength than the case where meso-porosity is absent. This is related to the specific geometrical distribution of voids. Theoretical predictions from micromechanical models, Eqs. (10) and (11), respectively denoted with ‘GSCM’ and ‘Rice’, are also reported.

of the porous material. In particular, an interaction is observed between the two scales of porosity (the sum between the two Φ_{macro} and Φ_{meso} is constant and equal to Φ). This emerges from the plots of the dimensionless peak strength and Young’s modulus reported in Fig. 8 as resulting from simulated stress-strain curves, functions of macro and meso-porosity Φ_{macro} and Φ_{meso} . Simple linear regression of the normalized overall properties obtained from our two-scale porosity analyses (depicted in Fig. 8) leads to the following approximations

$$\frac{\bar{E}}{E_{\text{matrix}}} = 0.905 - 1.401\Phi_{\text{macro}} - 0.868\Phi_{\text{meso}}, \quad R^2 = 0.913, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_{\text{matrix}}} = 0.610 - 1.303\Phi_{\text{macro}} - 0.704\Phi_{\text{meso}}, \quad R^2 = 0.748, \quad (13)$$

where R^2 is the coefficient of determination.

Crack patterns are found to be strongly influenced by meso-porosity at fixed values of macro-porosity, as shown in Fig. 9, where simulations of crack patterns in two portions of a sample (one framed green and the other red) are shown at different stages of loading, during a compression test for $\Phi_{\text{macro}} = 25\%$ and $\Phi_{\text{meso}} = 10\%$. Here, simulations reveal the existence of two mechanisms of failure affecting specimens characterized by double porosity: (i.) in the portion of the sample framed red, cracks nucleate at the edge of macro-pores, while meso-pores promote the development of a crack network, while (ii.) in the portion framed green, cracks nucleate near meso-pores and develop by joining macro-pores.

Crack paths in two-scale porous specimens. The presence of meso-porosity does not only affect the overall mechanical behavior of a specimen in terms of stiffness and strength, but also its failure. The meso-porosity enhances damage diffusion and promotes new fracture paths, different from those observed in the absence of meso pores, as visible in Fig. 10, for $\Phi_{\text{macro}} = 20\%$. Here crack patterns are analyzed in a region of a sample compressed at a fixed value $\bar{\epsilon} = -6.1 \times 10^{-2}$ of overall strain, but with different amounts of meso-porosity, equal to $\{0\%, 5\%, 10\%\}$. In the region reported on the left, the meso porosity diffuses the damage and inhibits macro crack growth. Differently, on the right, meso porosity, initially enhances crack growth through bridging of microcracks (compare results at $\Phi_{\text{meso}} = 0$ and 10%), while a further increase in meso porosity shields the material from macrocracking.

Fig. 8 | Dependence of the mechanical behavior of Biomorphic Apatite on the voids' size distribution. Effects of the meso porosity fraction on the dimensionless peak stress and Young's modulus as a function of the macro porosity (left) and vice-versa (right).

Direct comparisons between phase-field simulations of fracture growth in a porous material and micrographs obtained during compression tests on BA (performed at the MUSAM-Lab, financed with the ERC StG CA2PVM, Grant Agreement 306622, and the ERC PoC PHYSIC, Grant Agreement No. 737447, at IMT School, Lucca), is presented in Fig. 11. The tests were executed by placing prismatic samples in direct contact with two steel platens (lateral size 40 mm and thickness 5 mm) and compressed (using the tensile/compressive stage DEBEN 5000S inside the scanning electron microscope Zeiss EVO MA15) by imposing displacements. The tests were continued until complete failure of the samples. Two mechanisms of crack propagation can be observed in Fig. 11: cracks either nucleate in the proximity of large pores and develop horizontally (highlighted in the figure with green arrows), or they nucleate near meso pores, thus producing a fracture network, where macro and meso pores are connected (highlighted in the figure with white arrows). Results of simulations are not *coincident* with the fracture experiments, because the samples used for simulation are randomly generated and therefore not identical to those analyzed experimentally. Nevertheless, the mechanisms of crack nucleation and growth are the same.

Note that, while the test at higher magnification (reported in Fig. 11) was performed inside the SEM, the other was conducted in air with the same tensile/compressive stage, but examined with a confocal microscope (Leica DCM3D) with a magnification lens $10\times$. In this way, a larger portion of the sample was observed. Again, sub-horizontal cracks are observed (green arrows), connecting macro pores, while inclined cracks nucleated near meso pores and later coalesced to join a 'main' propagating crack (characterized by a characteristic tortuosity). Cracks originating from meso-pores can sometimes shield macro-pores, as clearly indicated by the white arrows. All these features are accurately reproduced in the simulations.

Fig. 12 presents a view of a failed sample at a larger scale than that of Fig. 11, right (photo taken in air with a confocal microscope Leica DCM3D). Here the simulation (reported in terms of phase field on the left and deformed mesh on the central part) captures the formation of an inclined zone of highly damaged material, where micro and macro cracks form a large, but localized, failure zone. Again, while the simulation was performed on a randomly generated specimen, the failure mode is strongly representative of real tests.

Fig. 9|Crack evolution in Biomorphic Apatite with multiple scale porosity using the phase-field. Simulated fracture evolution through phase-field during compression of a sample characterized by a macro-porosity $\Phi_{\text{macro}} = 25\%$ and meso-porosity $\Phi_{\text{meso}} = 10\%$. Meso-pores induce two failure mechanisms, either involving nucleation (a-b) and growth (c) of cracks, or connecting macro-pores (d-e) and ultimately leading to failure (e).

Fig. 10|Effects of voids of small size on crack nucleation and growth in Biomorphic Apatite. Cracks develop parallel to the loading direction in the simulated fracture evolution through phase field during compression of a sample characterized by a macro porosity 20% and different values of meso-porosity equal to {0% 5%, 10%}. The reported phase-field refers to an overall strain of $\bar{\epsilon} = -6.1 \times 10^{-2}$. Note that the amount of meso-porosity influences the mechanisms of fracture, so that an increase of this porosity may promote or inhibit crack growth.

4. Discussion

Simulations carried out with the phase-field approach to fracture on samples with cylindrical porosity (generated in-silico to model a porous ceramics obtained from wood, biomorphic apatite) show that the presence of two size-scales of porosity plays an important role in damage diffusion and fracture growth. In particular, the simulations (performed with an in-house developed finite element code, calibrated on brittle materials, available in the Supplementary materials) show that during compressive failure: (i.) fractures nucleate at pore boundaries and grow almost parallel to the direction of compression; (ii.) large pores induce crack nucleation, while small pores foster their propagation by connecting distantly located voids; (iii.) small pores cause the formation of micro-cracks, eventually promoting and propagating failure; (iv.) small pores diffuse damage and reduce the inclination of the softening branches in the overall stress-strain curves.

At a given value of the total porosity, specimens characterized by high values of meso-porosity exhibit mechanical properties, expressed through Young's modulus and peak stress, which are superior to those displayed by specimens with the same porosity but uniform. Therefore, the pore size distribution has to be considered a major influential parameter in the mechanical design of porous brittle materials, where the phase-field approach reveals its excellent potentialities.

Fig. 11 | Phase-field successfully reproduces crack propagation mechanisms in biomorphic apatite. Upper part on the left and lower part: experiments show crack propagation nearly parallel to the applied compressive stress. The same feature is found in the simulation on a randomly generated sample (thus not identical neither to the sample on the left nor to that in the lower part). The simulation was terminated at an overall strain of 6.5×10^{-2} . The photo in the upper part was made with a SEM, while the other with a confocal microscope (Leica DCM3D), during a compression test. Note that the tortuosity of the crack paths is the result of almost straight cracks connecting macro-pores (green arrows), while inclined cracks originate from micro-pores (white arrows).

Data availability

All the raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings are provided in the Appendix A, both in terms of finite element codes to generate and run the computational models, and in terms of key research results.

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Fig. 12|The phase-field (left) and the deformed mesh (centre) successfully reproduces failure patterns in a biomorphic apatite with 27% total porosity (photo on the right). The simulation is performed on a sample with the same meso and macro porosity of the real material, but with a random generation of voids. Even if the real sample is not identical to that tested in silico, the failure mode is the same.

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Appendix A. Supporting Material

Appendix A.1. Biomorphie Apatite

Two micrographs are reported in Extended Data Fig. 1, showing the cylindrical and non-overlapping nature of the porosity in the Biomorphie Apatite. The peculiar porosity results from the biomorphie transformation of rattan wood, used to produce the ceramic [13]. The voids do not overlap and run almost parallel to each other.

Extended Data Fig. 1 | The microscopic structure of biomorphie apatite. Two SEM micrographs showing the cylindrical nature of the porosity of Biomorphie Apatite, resulting from the micromorphie transformation of rattan wood. The photo on the left shows two orthogonal planes, one crossing and the other parallel to the axes of the cylindrical voids. The photo on right pertains to a section of a sample taken parallel to the axes of the cylindrical voids.

Appendix A.2. Code for the automatic generation of in-silico samples

The following code was implemented in the software Wolfram Mathematica 13.2 to generate samples through a random placing of circular voids in a rectangular specimen.

```
1 findPoints=  
2 Compile[{{n, _Integer},{lowX, _Real},{lowY, _Real}, {highX, _Real},{highY, _Real},{minD, _Real}},  
3 Block[{data = {{RandomReal[{lowX, highX}, 1][[1]],  
4 RandomReal[{lowY, highY}, 1][[1]]}}, k=1, rv, temp},  
5 While[k<n,  
6 rv = {RandomReal[{lowX, highX}, 1][[1]], RandomReal[{lowY, highY}, 1][[1]]};  
7 temp = Transpose[Transpose[data] - rv];  
8 If[Min[Sqrt[({#.#})]&/@ temp]>minD, data = Join[data, {rv}];  
9 k++;  
10 ];  
11 ];  
12 data]];  
13  
14 average =.; (* mean value of the normal distribution of voids' radii *)  
15 stdev =.; (* standard deviation of the normal distribution of voids' radii *)  
16 npts = 10; (* number of voids to be randomly placed in a rectangular specimen *)  
17 randomradius = RandomVariate[NormalDistribution[average,stdev],npts];  
18 minD = 2.05 Quantile[randomradius, 0.999]; (* to avoid overlapping voids *)  
19 lowX = 0;  
20 highX = 4.5; (* Width of the specimen *)  
21 lowY = 0;  
22 highY = 9; (* Height of the specimen *)  
23  
24 pts = findPoints[npts,lowX,lowY,highX,highY,minD];  
25
```

```

26 Graphics[{{EdgeForm[Black],White,Rectangle[{lowX,lowY}-1.5 Quantile[randomradius, 1],{highX,
    highY}+1.5 Quantile[randomradius, 1]}], Table[Circle[pts[[i]], randomradius[[i]], {i,1,
    Dimensions[pts][[1]]}]}]}]
27 porosity = Sum[\[Pi]randomradius[[i]]^2,{i,1,Dimensions[pts][[1]]}]/(highX highY) 100

```

Appendix A.3. An example of FEniCS code used for the phase-field simulations

The following code was written in Python language and implemented in FEniCS for the phase-field simulations of compression tests of rectangular samples characterized by 10% macro-porosity.

```

1 # Preliminaries and mesh
2 from dolfin import *
3 from mshr import *
4 from fenics import *
5 import sympy as sp
6 import numpy as np
7
8 N = 200 # mesh density
9
10 # Dimensions of the rectangular specimen.
11 L=4.5 # Dimension parallel to the loading direction
12 H=9
13
14 domain = Rectangle(Point(0.0,0.0), Point(L, H))\
15 -Circle(Point(3.0234,1.32474),0.200989)\
16 -Circle(Point(1.08572,0.914887),0.130479)\
17 -Circle(Point(1.90868,4.34213),0.121515)\
18 -Circle(Point(1.60387,5.6856),0.156055)\
19 -Circle(Point(1.19912,7.35778),0.131318)\
20 -Circle(Point(3.36847,3.88493),0.173114)\
21 -Circle(Point(2.90055,4.82629),0.178513)\
22 -Circle(Point(4.02467,2.21994),0.130005)\
23 -Circle(Point(0.962283,3.70378),0.12214)\
24 -Circle(Point(2.33,4.55591),0.131623)\
25 -Circle(Point(3.4486,5.76657),0.182436)\
26 -Circle(Point(1.91112,7.6117),0.164998)\
27 -Circle(Point(2.44688,0.72838),0.184461)\
28 -Circle(Point(1.70415,3.62776),0.180363)\
29 -Circle(Point(3.35107,6.89623),0.164833)\
30 -Circle(Point(3.27043,1.75659),0.181709)\
31 -Circle(Point(2.34352,1.35264),0.159497)\
32 -Circle(Point(3.03574,8.51386),0.152183)\
33 -Circle(Point(1.46163,2.22812),0.16439)\
34 -Circle(Point(1.5093,8.08228),0.163185)\
35 -Circle(Point(2.17844,6.26656),0.102296)\
36 -Circle(Point(1.99024,6.75547),0.133753)\
37 -Circle(Point(3.66352,8.35351),0.172959)\
38 -Circle(Point(1.03372,5.5871),0.159102)\
39 -Circle(Point(2.93496,2.88294),0.157626)\
40 -Circle(Point(3.87797,1.78228),0.15366)\
41 -Circle(Point(2.79145,8.09159),0.177494)\
42 -Circle(Point(3.35845,5.18456),0.18442)\
43 -Circle(Point(1.0558,4.18037),0.141059)\
44 -Circle(Point(3.74802,0.691879),0.133691)\
45 -Circle(Point(3.43903,7.45755),0.141225)\
46 -Circle(Point(0.455644,1.29338),0.217278)\
47 -Circle(Point(1.61206,0.47063),0.161412)\
48 -Circle(Point(0.811631,3.01581),0.172358)\
49 -Circle(Point(0.788551,2.30062),0.184847)\
50 -Circle(Point(1.12189,8.50223),0.123125)\
51 -Circle(Point(3.24528,0.89577),0.168204)\
52 -Circle(Point(3.35042,4.39078),0.160364)\
53 -Circle(Point(2.40094,3.94387),0.206106)\
54 -Circle(Point(2.20688,8.31152),0.154431)\
55 -Circle(Point(1.51481,4.82766),0.199603)\

```

```

56 -Circle(Point(2.88458,6.14344),0.171904)\
57 -Circle(Point(2.0923,5.0049),0.157516)\
58 -Circle(Point(1.80456,1.13777),0.158846)\
59 -Circle(Point(2.41821,3.50223),0.142688)\
60 -Circle(Point(2.91964,5.57736),0.147211)\
61 -Circle(Point(2.05032,5.51792),0.188997)\
62 -Circle(Point(2.48433,5.62876),0.174551)\
63 -Circle(Point(1.06665,1.52626),0.174677)\
64 -Circle(Point(2.43591,2.99175),0.146721)\
65 -Circle(Point(2.10898,1.85966),0.130821)\
66 -Circle(Point(0.637225,5.22015),0.156965)\
67 -Circle(Point(0.926142,6.79028),0.191514)\
68 -Circle(Point(0.958435,0.43857),0.140543)\
69 -Circle(Point(2.62284,7.55941),0.129576)
70
71 mesh = generate_mesh(domain, N)      # Generate mesh of the domain
72
73 # Define Space
74 V = FunctionSpace(mesh, 'CG', 1)
75 W = VectorFunctionSpace(mesh, 'CG', 1)
76 WW = FunctionSpace(mesh, 'DG', 0)
77 p, q = TrialFunction(V), TestFunction(V)
78 pnw, pold, Hold = Function(V), Function(V), Function(V)
79
80 # Introduce manually the parameters for a linear elastic perfectly brittle
81 # material under plane stress loading
82 E= 70                                # Young's Modulus
83 nuu = 0.25                            # Poisson ratio
84 lmbda = E*nuu/(1-nuu**2)             # First Lamé' constant
85 mu = E/(2*(1+nuu))                  # Second Lamé' constant
86 Gc=0.0025                            # Griffith critical surface energy
87 l= 0.012                              # Regularisation length
88
89 tol=1E-8
90 kappa=1e-6                            # Residual stiffness.
91
92 # Introducing strain energy density split
93
94 # Measures of strain
95 def epsilon(u):
96     return sym(grad(u))
97
98 # Positive strain: strain associated with positive eigenvalues
99 # of the strain tensor
100 def strn_p(u):
101     t = sym(grad(u))
102
103     v00= (t[0, 0] + t[1, 1])/2 + sqrt(((t[0,0]-t[1,1])/2)**2+(t[1,0])**2)
104     v01= 0
105     v10= 0
106     v11= (t[0, 0] + t[1, 1])/2 - sqrt(((t[0,0]-t[1,1])/2)**2+(t[1,0])**2)
107
108     cons1 = 1/sqrt(1+((v00-t[0,0])/t[1,0])**2)
109     cons2 = 1/sqrt(1+((v11-t[0,0])/t[1,0])**2)
110     w00 = cons1
111     w01 = cons2
112     w10 = cons1*(v00-t[0,0])/t[1,0]
113     w11 = cons2*(v11-t[0,0])/t[1,0]
114
115     wp = ([w00,w01],[w10,w11])
116     wp = as_tensor(wp)
117
118     wp_tr = ([w00,w10],[w01,w11])
119     wp_tr = as_tensor(wp_tr)
120

```

```

121     v00 = conditional(gt(v00,0.0),v00,0.0)
122     v11 = conditional(gt(v11,0.0),v11,0.0)
123
124     vp = ([v00,v01],[v10,v11])
125     vp = as_tensor(vp)
126     return wp*vp*wp_tr
127
128 # Negative strain: strain associated with negative eigenvalues
129 # of the strain tensor
130 def strn_n(u):
131     t = sym(grad(u))
132
133     v00= (t[0, 0] + t[1, 1])/2 + sqrt(((t[0,0]-t[1,1])/2)**2+(t[1,0])**2)
134     v01= 0
135     v10= 0
136     v11= (t[0, 0] + t[1, 1])/2 - sqrt(((t[0,0]-t[1,1])/2)**2+(t[1,0])**2)
137
138     cons1 = 1/sqrt(1+((v00-t[0,0])/t[1,0])**2)
139     cons2 = 1/sqrt(1+((v11-t[0,0])/t[1,0])**2)
140     w00 = cons1
141     w01 = cons2
142     w10 = cons1*(v00-t[0,0])/t[1,0]
143     w11 = cons2*(v11-t[0,0])/t[1,0]
144
145     wn = ([w00,w01],[w10,w11])
146     wn = as_tensor(wn)
147
148     wn_tr = ([w00,w10],[w01,w11])
149     wn_tr = as_tensor(wn_tr)
150
151     v00 = conditional(lt(v00,0.0),v00,0.0)
152     v11 = conditional(lt(v11,0.0),v11,0.0)
153
154     vn = ([v00,v01],[v10,v11])
155     vn = as_tensor(vn)
156     return wn*vn*wn_tr
157
158 #Part of the energy associated with the positive strain
159 def psi(u):
160     return 0.5*lambda*(0.5*(tr(epsilon(u))+abs(tr(epsilon(u)))))**2
161     +mu*tr(strn_p(u)*strn_p(u))
162
163 #Part of the energy associated with the negative strain
164 def psi_n(u):
165     return 0.5*lambda*(0.5*(tr(epsilon(u))-abs(tr(epsilon(u)))))**2
166     +mu*tr(strn_n(u)*strn_n(u))
167
168 # Strain history function, accounting for the irreversibility of crack formation
169 def H(uold,unew,Hold):
170     return conditional(lt(psi(uold),psi(unew)),psi(unew),Hold)
171
172 # Boundary conditions
173 right = CompiledSubDomain("near(x[0], 4.5) && on_boundary")
174 left = CompiledSubDomain("near(x[0], 0.0) && on_boundary")
175 def left1(x, on_boundary):
176     return abs(x[1]-4.5) < 1e-01 and on_boundary
177
178 load = Expression("t", t = 0.0, degree=1)
179 bcleft = DirichletBC(W.sub(0), Constant(0.0), left )
180 bcleft1= DirichletBC(W.sub(1), Constant(0.0), left1)
181 bcrigh= DirichletBC(W.sub(0), load, right)
182 bc_u = [bcrigh, bcleft, bcleft1]
183 boundaries = MeshFunction("size_t", mesh, mesh.topology().dim() - 1)
184 boundaries.set_all(0)
185 left.mark(boundaries,1)

```

```

186 ds = Measure("ds")(subdomain_data=boundaries)
187 n = FacetNormal(mesh)
188
189 # Cauchy stress.
190 def sigma(u):
191     return 2.0*mu*epsilon(u)+lambda*tr(epsilon(u))*Identity(len(u))
192
193 # Cauchy stress associated with the positive strain energy
194 def sigma_p(u):
195     return lambda*0.5*(tr(epsilon(u))+abs(tr(epsilon(u))))*Identity(len(u))
196     +2.0*mu*strn_p(u)
197
198 # Cauchy stress associated with the negative strain energy
199 def sigma_n(u):
200     return lambda*0.5*(tr(epsilon(u))-abs(tr(epsilon(u))))*Identity(len(u))
201     +2.0*mu*strn_n(u)
202
203 x = SpatialCoordinate(mesh)
204
205 du = TrialFunction(W)
206 v = TestFunction(W)
207
208 # Variational form
209 unew, uold = Function(W), Function(W)
210
211 # set up solution functions
212 u = Function(W,name='displacement')
213
214 # The way the eigenvalues are computed one cannot allow
215 # a constant value of u at the start
216
217 u_array = u.vector().get_local()
218 u_array = np.random.rand(len(u_array))
219 u.vector()[:] = u_array
220
221 # Weak form of the mechanical problem
222 F_u = (((1.0-pold)**2+kappa)*inner(grad(v),sigma_p(u))+inner(grad(v),sigma_n(u)))*dx
223 J_u = derivative(F_u, u, du)
224 p_disp = NonlinearVariationalProblem(F_u, u, bc_u, J_u)
225 solver_disp = NonlinearVariationalSolver(p_disp)
226
227 # Weak form of the evolutive problem
228 E_phi = (Gc*1*inner(grad(p),grad(q))+
229 ((Gc/1)+2.0*H(uold,unew,Hold))*inner(p,q)-2.0*H(uold,unew,Hold)*q)*dx
230 p_phi = LinearVariationalProblem(lhs(E_phi), rhs(E_phi),pnew)
231 solver_phi = LinearVariationalSolver(p_phi)
232
233 # Initialization of the iterative procedure and output requests
234 t = 0
235 u_r1 = -1.0*1e-3 # Imposed displacement
236 u_r2 = -3.0*1e-5
237 deltaT = 1.0
238
239 conc_f = File("./PHASE/phi.pvd")
240 u_f = File("./DISPL/u.pvd")
241 fname = open('ForcevsDisp.txt','w')
242 fname1 = open('Strain_energy.txt','w')
243 fname2 = open('Dissipated_energy.txt','w')
244
245 # Definition of the total elastic energy and total dissipated energy
246 def E_strain(u,pold):
247     return (((1.0-pold)**2+kappa)*psi(u)+psi_n(u))*dx
248 def E_dissip(p):
249     return ((Gc/2)*1*inner(grad(p),grad(p))+(Gc/(2*1))*p**2)*dx
250

```

```

251 T1 = 400
252 T2 = 0
253 Tmax=T1+T2
254
255
256 # Staggered scheme
257 while t<=Tmax:
258     t += deltaT
259     if(t<=T1):
260         load.t+=u_r1
261     if(t>T1):
262         load.t+=u_r2
263
264     solver_disp.solve()
265
266     uold.assign(uneu)
267     neu.assign(u)
268
269     solver_phi.solve()
270
271     pold.assign(pneu)
272
273     Hold.assign(project(psi(uneu), WW))
274
275     print ('Iterations:', iter, ', Total time', t)
276     if (t % 5) == 0: # stampa ogni 5 timestep
277         conc_f << pneu
278         u_f << neu
279     Traction = dot(sigma(uneu),n)
280     fx = Traction[0]*ds(1)
281     fname1.write(str(t) + "\t")
282     fname1.write(str(assemble(E_strain(uneu,pneu))) + "\n")
283     fname2.write(str(t) + "\t")
284     fname2.write(str(assemble(E_dissip(pneu))) + "\n")
285     print ('traction:', iter, ', Total time', t, fx)
286     #fname.write(str(t*u_r) + "\t")
287     fname.write(str(assemble(fx)) + "\n")
288
289 fname.close()
290 print ('Simulation completed')

```

Sensitivity of the code to the mesh size was tested in order to calibrate the mesh size for subsequent numerical analyses. Extended Data Fig. 2 shows the results.

Here, compression tests for three values of single-scale porosity are simulated with generated in-silico specimens. Simulations are performed with 5 different meshes of increasing number of elements, to assess the sensitivity to the mesh refinement. Meshes, generated with isoparametric linear triangular finite elements, are characterized by the number h of nodes (examples are reported in Fig. 3), discretizing the side L of samples parallel to the loading, so that the values $h = \{100, 150, 200, 250, 300\}$ have been considered. In order to find the value of h for which the solution becomes mesh-independent, strength (in terms of overall peak stress $\bar{\sigma}$) and stiffness (in terms of overall Young's Modulus \bar{E}) have been evaluated. Results are presented in Fig. 2, where \bar{E} and $\bar{\sigma}$ are made dimensionless respectively through division by the Young's modulus and by the value of the peak stress in tension, both referred to the matrix material. Fig. 2 shows that independence of mesh size is achieved for $h \geq 200$, so that $h = 200$ is selected for the subsequent evaluations.

Appendix A.4. Single-scale porosity

A schematic representation of the samples and the loading conditions used in the numerical simulations when a single scale of porosity is only present, is sketched in the inset of Extended Data Fig. 3. Results of numerical simulations of compression tests of porous brittle material using the phase-field approach to

Extended Data Fig. 2 | Sensitivity analysis of the phasefield simulation on mesh refinement. Convergence of peak stress and overall Young’s modulus for increasing number of nodes of the finite element mesh in the direction parallel to loading.

fracture are summarized in Extended Data Tab. 1, where the overall Young’s modulus (\bar{E}) and Peak stress ($\bar{\sigma}$) are reported for each specimen along with its porosity.

Overall stress-strain curves shown in Extended Data Fig. 3 have been obtained by averaging over ten simulations, for each level of macro-porosity (sketched on the top of the figure). The corresponding evolution of the phase-field, representing crack patterns, is shown in Extended Data Fig. 3, along with the deformed mesh. As clearly visible, cracks progressively develop parallel to the direction of the applied load. Extended Data Fig. 3 shows that the model can effectively capture damage nucleation, fracture propagation, and the final failure mechanism.

Well-formed crack patterns at a strain level close to collapse are reported in the upper part of Extended Data Fig. 3 for all samples shown in Extended Data Fig. 3. In the lower part of the same figure, the phase-field shows that cracks grow parallel to the loading direction, independently of the porosity. To highlight fracture growth, the lower part of the figure reports details of the samples at two levels of overall strain $\bar{\epsilon}$ ranging between 5×10^{-2} and 7×10^{-2} .

Appendix A.5. Strain within the samples

Simulations of compression tests on porous material are carried out until overall strains equal to 0.1. These values are moderately large and can be decomposed into a relatively small strain in the matrix material and large rigid-body displacements of blocks separated by intense zones of damage. In fact, the maps of the three strain components reported in Extended Data Fig. 4 show that intense strains only occur in narrow zones of highly deformed material.

Appendix A.6. Two-scale porosity

In Extended Data Tab. 2 a summary of the results is reported (in terms of overall Young’s Modulus and peak stress) of the simulations carried out for the samples characterized by two scales of porosity.

Φ_{macro}	\bar{E} [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}$ [MPa]	Φ_{macro}	\bar{E} [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}$ [MPa]
0%	70.00	7.27	25%	39.19	1.80
5%	61.87	4.42	25%	39.84	1.78
5%	61.69	4.61	25%	38.50	1.55
5%	62.05	4.37	25%	37.93	1.47
5%	61.78	4.49	25%	38.65	1.83
5%	61.83	4.76	25%	37.77	1.39
5%	61.86	4.60	25%	37.77	1.89
5%	62.20	4.52	25%	38.51	1.91
5%	61.79	4.84	25%	38.95	1.98
5%	62.16	4.31	30%	37.13	1.87
5%	62.02	4.39	30%	35.73	1.68
10%	54.88	3.40	30%	34.69	1.65
10%	55.56	3.47	30%	34.15	1.26
10%	55.55	3.16	30%	34.32	1.54
10%	55.04	3.30	30%	34.19	1.27
10%	55.30	3.66	30%	33.86	1.57
10%	55.34	3.29	30%	33.05	1.48
10%	55.34	3.11	30%	32.64	1.42
10%	55.03	3.51	30%	33.82	1.52
10%	55.14	3.30	32%	33.72	1.67
10%	55.18	3.16	32%	32.75	1.54
15%	51.09	3.26	32%	33.95	1.59
15%	48.97	2.62	35%	29.47	1.14
15%	49.26	2.63	35%	30.03	1.12
15%	49.27	2.67	35%	29.37	1.30
15%	48.92	2.69	35%	29.40	1.23
15%	48.84	2.77	35%	29.82	1.25
15%	48.29	2.79	35%	29.13	1.22
15%	48.64	2.45	35%	30.01	1.39
15%	49.02	3.00	35%	30.29	1.24
15%	48.34	2.79	35%	30.35	1.34
20%	46.15	2.43	35%	30.40	1.24
20%	43.67	2.21	40%	22.21	0.79
20%	44.30	2.18	40%	23.33	0.97
20%	42.82	1.88	40%	23.37	0.94
20%	43.16	2.12	40%	25.49	0.98
20%	43.08	2.16	40%	26.01	1.15
20%	42.95	1.93	40%	26.45	1.06
20%	42.44	1.87	40%	26.24	1.17
20%	43.77	2.20	40%	26.25	1.16
20%	43.07	2.26	40%	25.88	1.04
25%	41.57	2.01	40%	26.34	1.12

Extended Data Table 1 | Overall properties of specimen with single scale voids. Summary of the overall properties of single scale brittle porous specimen with a single scale of porosity according to phase-field approach to fracture mechanics.

Extended Data Fig. 3 | Phasefield simulation of crack propagation in biomorphic apatite, where only one scale of porosity is considered. Deformed meshes (upper part) at an overall strain close to the strain at the collapse and phase-field evolution (lower part) at two levels of overall strain $\bar{\epsilon}$ ranging between 5×10^{-2} and 7×10^{-2} , for samples of different porosity, tested under uniaxial compression in the horizontal direction.

Extended Data Fig. 4 | Components of the strain tensor in a specimen with 25% macro-porosity for an imposed lateral displacement of 0.2 mm, corresponding to an estimated average axial strain of $\bar{\epsilon} \approx 0.04$.

Φ_{macro}	Φ_{meso}	Φ	\bar{E} [MPa]	$\bar{\sigma}$ [MPa]
0%	0%	0%	70.00	7.27
10%	0%	10%	54.35	3.34
15%	0%	15%	48.66	2.52
10%	5%	15%	50.49	3.00
15%	2%	17%	46.85	2.40
15%	3%	18%	46.12	2.35
15%	5%	20%	44.87	2.34
20%	0%	20%	46.15	2.43
10%	10%	20%	46.87	2.72
15%	10%	25%	41.43	2.26
25%	0%	25%	37.26	1.67
20%	5%	25%	40.56	2.07
25%	2%	27%	35.62	1.52
25%	3%	28%	35.09	1.53
25%	5%	30%	34.04	1.51
30%	0%	30%	33.31	1.40
20%	10%	30%	37.65	2.00
25%	7%	32%	32.45	1.45
30%	2%	32%	31.76	1.31
32%	0%	32%	30.83	1.22
30%	3%	33%	31.39	1.31
32%	2%	34%	29.32	1.10
25%	10%	35%	31.62	1.44
30%	5%	35%	30.30	1.26
32%	3%	35%	28.87	1.08
35%	0%	35%	29.67	1.28
32%	5%	37%	28.08	1.05
35%	5%	40%	26.86	1.17
30%	10%	40%	28.17	1.24
40%	0%	40%	25.50	0.95
32%	10%	42%	25.92	1.01
40%	2%	42%	24.06	0.88
40%	3%	43%	23.70	0.87
35%	10%	45%	26.01	1.13
40%	5%	45%	23.01	0.86
40%	10%	50%	21.42	0.85

Extended Data Table 2|Overall response of specimen with voids of different size. Summary of the results – in terms of overall Young’s Modulus and peak stress – of the simulations carried out for the samples with two scales of porosity.